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PMT Pre-calibration for SABRE South

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Abstract

The DAMA [1] experiments have detected a modulating signal compatible with dark matter for 20 years with a combined significance of 12.9. A result in tension for a spin independent WIMP with null results from large noble gas experiments. This is the motivation for SABRE [2] (Sodium iodide with Active Background Rejection) South experiment. A NaI(Tl) based replication of the DAMA experiment. It is designed to test the DAMA modulation results using the same NaI(Tl) crystal target readout by 14 Hamamatsu R11065 photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) with a 1 keVee energy threshold.

This poster will report on the photomultiplier characterisation test bench developed for the photomultipliers of SABRE South and preliminary results from the first test batch of PMTs. This includes studies of the single photon response, quantum efficiency, and dark noise. The results of the photomultiplier characterisation are crucial to model and understand the low energy performance of the SABRE South experiment. This is crucial to ensure that SABRE South can provide an accurate and significant measurement of the DAMA signal.

Figure 1: Photos of the R5912 VETO (Left) and R11065 Crystal (Right) PMTs.

1 Introduction

The DAMA [1] (LNGS, Italy) experiment has detected a modulating signal in NaI(Tl) compatible with dark matter for 20 years, with a combined significance of 12.9σ . This signal to date remains in tension with other dark matter detection experiments. This tension motivates a model independent test of the DAMA modulation with NaI crystals as target material with current attempts yet to confirm or exclude the DAMA signal. There are a number of experiments aiming to recreate and improve on DAMA including, ANAIS-112 [3], COSINE-100 [4] and SABRE [5]. Current results from ANAIS and COSINE, have yet to conclusively confirm or exclude the DAMA signal. The SABRE experiment is an upcoming experiment with the aim to test the DAMA Modulation in both hemispheres. SABRE North will be located at LNGS the same site as DAMA and SABRE South at the newly build Stawell Underground Physics Laboratory (SUPL) in Australia. Having twin detectors in the north and south hemisphere allows SABRE to distinguish a potential dark matter signal from background variations due to seasons. In order to do this SABRE requires low background PMTs with high single photon detection efficiency coupled to the crystals as well as a highly efficient veto system to reach backgrounds below DAMA. It is therefore essential that all PMTs are tested prior to the installation in the detector. These proceedings report on the development of the pre-calibration process for SABRE South R11065 and R5912 PMTs.

2 Pre-Calibration

2.1 Test bench

Two test setups have been developed in order to conduct pre-calibration measurements of our PMTs these are shown in Fig.[2], used for (left) temperature controlled dark rate measurement and (right) single photo-electron calibrations. The first of the two set-ups consists of a freezer with a 55W heater placed inside. The PMT will then be placed inside of a dark box within the freezer. The set-up is monitored using four temperature probes within the box with three next to the PMT this allows us to monitor the temperature through out the runs. The second set-up consists of an aluminum box with a pico-second pulsed laser operating at a wavelength of 405 nm. The light from the laser is fed in via a fibre optic cable and passes through an ND4 filter ($\approx 10^4$ attenuation) followed by a beam splitter. For both of these setups PMTs are powered by CAEN SY5527 multichannel power supply systems and digitised using CAEN V1730 (500 MS/s) digitiser.

Figure 2: Experimental set-up for pre-calibration studies, (Left) temperature controlled dark rate studies and (Right) single photo-electron (SPE) setup consisting of a pico-second pulsed laser at 405 nm

3 Dark Rate study

The SABRE South detector will be operated at 22°C. The main (non-radiogenic) background in our detectors when operating at room temperature is the dark rate which is predominantly caused by thermal electrons emitted from the PMT photocathode. Understanding this rate with respect to temperature will allow us to understand the contribution of this effect through our analyses and will be crucial to having a proper understanding of our detector response.

Dark rate for each of the PMTs were measured at varying voltages and temperatures to understand it's dependence. At each temperature 4 hours are given to allow for thermalisation of the PMT additionally 30 minutes are given for stabilisation at each voltage, each run is taken over 5 minutes. The dark rates are then calculated counting the events above a threshold of 1.5 mV (0.2 SPE). The results of the studies for the R11065 and R5912 are shown in Fig.[3]. It can be seen that the results are in good agreement with the relationship provided by Hamamatsu Eqn.1 [6] relating the dark rate to the operating temperature.

$$R \propto T^{\frac{5}{4}} \times e^{-\frac{q_e \Psi}{KT}} \quad (1)$$

Where T is the absolute temperature (K), q_e the electron charge, K Boltzmann constant and Ψ the work function.

4 Gain Calibration

The other key characteristics for our PMTs is the calibration of the gain which has already been completed for all of the R5912 and a sub sample of the R11065. This makes use of the laser dark

Figure 3: Dark rate as a function of temperature at various voltages.

Figure 4: Time difference spectrum, the red region is the selected region (20ns wide).

box set-up shown in Fig.[2] right. The set-up has been calibrated to have a mean occupancy below 0.05 which was achieved by controlling the laser power and applying ND Filters to the laser light. The set-up allows us to complete measurements of two PMTs simultaneously. The hardware trigger requires that we obtain a signal greater than 1 mV on one of the PMT and the trigger occurs 500 ns into the collection window. We further require that laser and PMT trigger are in a 20 ns coincidence window to obtain a pure sample of laser-correlated events. Determination of the gain is based on fitting our spectrum using Eqn.2 from [7].

$$\mu = \sum_{n=1}^{n=4} ((1-p) \cdot G(Q_{PE}, \sigma_{PE}) + p \cdot G(\delta Q_{PE}, \delta \sigma_{PE}))^n \quad (2)$$

Where $G(Q_{PE}, \sigma_{PE})$ is a gaussian with mean Q and standard deviation σ , p is the poissonian probability of under-amplified signal, and δ is the under-amplified scale parameter. An example is shown of this fit result in Fig.[5], where the parameters associated with the 1 Photo-electron (PE) peak, width of the under-amplified pulse and mean occupancy are floated. Parameters for the 2, 3 and 4 PE components are calculated relative to the 1PE and under-amplified values. These fits are repeated on a number of different voltages within 1300V - 1750V (1800V), the safe operating voltages for the R11065 (R5912) PMTs. We can then extract the gain from the mean 1 PE charge of the fit model. The result of this is displayed in Fig.[6].

5 Method verification

We further made use of dark rate data from section 3, which would predominantly consist of thermionic electrons emitted from the photocathode. Allowing us to verify our results and explore the possibility of measuring the in-situ gain measurements for our R11065 PMTs as there is no planned optical calibration in the crystal modules. Data selection for this data is based on the expectation that the peak position of the event should occur within 25 ns of our

Figure 5: The Single Photo-electron charge spectrum fitted with eqn.2.

Figure 6: R11065 PMT gain characterisation, (Left) results for Laser triggered data set. (Right) Comparison for Laser triggered and dark counts (thermal).

DAQ trigger position. The outputs of this selection was then fitted with Eqn.2, the fit region was adjusted to exclude the pedestal in our data as this would need to be modelled using additional parameters. These fits are shown in Fig.[6] and are consistent with our Laser based method. This shows that dark counts can be used for PMT gain monitoring in the full experiment

6 Conclusion

Pre-calibration efforts for the SABRE South PMTs (R5912 and R11065) are ongoing and will be completed before the installation of the SABRE South detectors. This process will include at its core the dark rate and gain calibration efforts with additional measurement of the QE (Quantum Efficiency), linearity and timing expected to be completed on a subset of our PMTs. The pre-calibration set up and results are currently being written up for future publication with additional exploration into ML models for further background suppression. Additional details on the PMT and pre-calibration process are described in the SABRE South Technical Design Report [2].

References

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